

3D Fibre Orientation Measurements with the Confocal Laser Scanning Microscope

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ABSTRACT

High quality data on the 3D spatial distributions of glass and carbon fibres in fibre reinforced composites are important for assessing the effectiveness of different processing conditions and also for modelling the thermal and mechanical properties of the composites. The realtime computer analysis of elliptical fibre images in a polished 2D section by optical reflection microscopy has become the standard method for the automatic (or semi-automatic) derivation of fibre orientation distributions. This paper compares fibre orientation measurements taken by both optical reflection microscopy and confocal microscopy techniques and discusses the maximum useable depth Δz_m of the confocal technique for different fibre/matrix combinations.

Keywords: 3D fibre orientations, CLSM, fibre reinforced composites

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past few years, a large area, high spatial resolution 2D image analyser has been developed for studying glass and carbon fibre orientation distributions in composites [1],[2]. Each sample is physically sectioned, polished and analysed by optical reflection microscopy. Most of the work has involved the measurement of orientations of well aligned, long and short fibre reinforcements[3]. However, a programme was initiated recently to test the predictions of the 'pseudo-affine' model[4] for different draw ratios of hydrostatically extruded, short glass fibre reinforced polyoxymethylene(POM). In the course of this investigation, the limitations of the standard, optical reflection microscopy technique have become apparent and the confocal laser scanning microscope (CLSM) technique has been explored[5].

Ideally, a perfect measurement technique for fibre orientations should be able to compute the in-plane angle, Φ and the colatitude angle, θ . If one adopts the coordinate system convention shown in Figure 1, it is clear that a single physical section, which produces elliptical fibre images, can yield colatitude values between $0^\circ \leq \theta < 90^\circ$ and in-plane values $0^\circ \leq \Phi < 180^\circ$.

In other words, there is an ambiguity in the value of θ , because the same elliptical image is produced by a fibre oriented by colatitude angle θ or $(180 - \theta)$. Some groups have devised techniques e.g. etching[6], acoustic banding[7] to remove this ambiguity by operator interaction

Figure 1. 3D coordinate convention adopted. For quadrants (a) and (b), $\theta = \tan^{-1}(\Delta r/\Delta z)$ and for quadrants (c) and (d), $\theta = 180^\circ - \tan^{-1}(\Delta r/\Delta z)$, where Δz is the separation between sections and Δr is the shift of image centres from one section to another.

but, if a second section plane could be accurately registered with the first plane, it is clear that, in principle, the θ, Φ values could be derived from the shift in the fibre image centres, Δx and Δy .

$$\Delta r = \sqrt{(\Delta x^2 + \Delta y^2)} \quad (1)$$

$$\theta = \tan^{-1}(\Delta r/\Delta z) \quad (2)$$

$$\Phi = \tan^{-1}(\Delta y/\Delta x) \quad (3)$$

If Δy , defined as $(y_{\text{upper}} - y_{\text{lower}})$ is +ve, equation (2) is valid but, if Δy is -ve, then

$$\theta = 180 - \tan^{-1}(\Delta r/\Delta z) \quad (4)$$

However, the pattern matching of fibre images to high spatial precision from two, physical sections is computationally intensive. The two sections will be translated and rotated in relation to each other and, if the microtoming process has created parallel section planes, an estimate must be made of the amount of material removed (by microtoming and polishing) between the sections. Despite these unknowns, a sample which is a few mm square will have thousands of fibre images which can be used to pattern match. Although the ellipticity of each image on the first plane gives an estimate of the (θ, Φ) of each fibre and hence a 'first guess' at the likely position of that fibre's image on the second plane, the θ ambiguity and errors in (θ, Φ) for near vertical fibres increases the computational complexity.

2. CONFOCAL MICROSCOPY

The confocal laser scanning microscope (CLSM) has the ability to take perfectly registered, optical sections at and below the surface of many materials[8]. Most published applications of the technique have been in the biological and physiological areas of research. Over the past few years, glass fibre reinforced polyoxymethylene (POM) samples have been studied and Figure 2 shows the fluorescence signals from optical sections taken with a separation of $\Delta z = 1\mu\text{m}$. Note the characteristic 'halo' around the fibres, which implies that the fluorescence is linked to the 'sizing' agents coating the fibres.

The BIORAD MRC series of confocal microscopes has three different modes of operation - reflection, fluorescence and photon counting. All of the measurements reported in the paper have been taken in fluorescence. A NIKON oil immersion objective, NA 1.4 and x60 magnification has been used.

If the transparency of a composite allows optical sections to be taken at depths, $\Delta z \geq 10\mu\text{m}$, there is a considerable improvement in the precision of measurement of both θ and Φ , compared to optical reflection microscopy. The challenge is to devise robust image processing algorithms which maximise Δz and which enable fibre positions to be measured over a large area (mms x mms) with high spatial resolution.

Figure 2. A set of optical sections taken every $1\mu\text{m}$ into the glass fibres in POM sample.

3. COMPARISON OF CONFOCAL AND OPTICAL REFLECTION TECHNIQUES

The CLSM has been used to illustrate the limitations of the 2D technique in the following way. Firstly, the surface layer images were scanned and a 'moments' algorithm[9] produced an estimate of θ_{ab} , Φ_{ab} for each fibre (as if a conventional 2D image analyser had made the measurements). Next, an optical section was made at a depth, $\Delta z = 10 \mu\text{m}$, and, from the shift of image centre coordinates, a new estimate of colatitude θ_{xy} and in-plane angle Φ_{xy} for each fibre was derived for comparison (see equations 2, 3 and 4). The results are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Whereas $0^\circ \leq \theta_{ab} < 90^\circ$, the CLSM shift of centres gives $0^\circ \leq \theta_{xy} < 180^\circ$ and hence Figure 3 shows a splitting of these two measures. Also, it is clear that the discrepancy between the two measurements increases for near perpendicular fibres and, on the assumption that the θ_{ab} values are more suspect, it would appear that orientations $\theta_{ab} \leq 30^\circ$ have appreciable error. The situation could be improved for higher system magnifications, but then data acquisition would take longer. Similarly, Figure 4 shows that for $45^\circ \leq \theta_{xy} < 135^\circ$, there is good agreement between the moments technique and the shift of centres technique but, outside of this range, the errors introduced by scanning a single section increase dramatically for near perpendicular fibres.

3.1. Fibre orientation measurements of well aligned composites

If the composites under investigation are well aligned and of high packing fraction, the 2D image analyser system can be particularly effective, provided that the sample is cut at a large angle to the preferred fibre axis (say, $\alpha = 45^\circ$) and the θ_α , Φ_α fibre orientations transformed back to a measurement plane perpendicular to the preferred axis. The transformation equations are [10]:

$$\theta = \cos^{-1}(\sin \alpha \cdot \sin \theta_\alpha \cdot \sin \Phi_\alpha + \cos \alpha \cdot \cos \theta_\alpha) \quad (5)$$

$$\Phi = \tan^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos \alpha \cdot \sin \theta_\alpha \cdot \sin \Phi_\alpha - \sin \alpha \cdot \cos \theta_\alpha}{\sin \theta_\alpha \cos \Phi_\alpha}\right) \quad (6)$$

Note that the moments technique assumes that the fibres are rigid cylinders of circular cross-section. Experience suggests that this is a good assumption for glass and some carbon fibres, but certainly not the case for Kevlar and other aramid fibres. The 'shift of centres' technique is valid for any fibre cross-section, assuming only that there is no twist or areal difference in cross-sections over a distance $10 < \Delta z \leq 30 \mu\text{m}$.

4. INITIAL SURVEY OF POLYMER COMPOSITES

It was decided to initiate a survey of fluorescence signals from various combinations of fillers and polymer matrices in order to assess the potential of the CLSM technique for 3D fibre orientation measurements. At the time of writing, this survey is at an early stage, but it is nevertheless possible to make a number of general statements.

4.1. Reinforcements

(a) Glass fibre reinforcements are easier to distinguish from the matrix in CLSM fluorescence mode than in the conventional 2D optical reflection microscopy. Special surface preparation is required to provide good contrast between fibre and matrix [11] in optical reflection mode, but with the CLSM either halo's are seen (if the matrix does not normally fluoresce) or the glass fibres look dark within a fluorescing matrix.

Figure 3. Correlation between θ_{xy} (derived from the shift of centres between sections) and θ_{ab} (derived from the ellipticity of fibre images on a single section), glass fibres in POM.

Figure 4. Modulus of the discrepancy between Φ_{xy} (derived from the shift of centres) and Φ_{ab} (derived from the ellipticity of fibre images) as a function of colatitude, θ_{xy} , glass fibres in POM.

(b) Carbon fibre reinforcements, especially at packing fractions $v_f \geq 40\%$, when viewed in fluorescence give a surface fibre/matrix contrast as good as the optical reflection technique but, unless the fibres are well aligned, the CLSM technique gives a maximum useable depth Δz_m of only a few micrometres. If the fibres are well aligned, $\Delta z_m = 10 \mu\text{m}$.

(c) Kevlar fibres show irregular cross-sections at the surface level and as the CLSM attempts to take an optical section below the surface, the opacity increases as for carbon fibres. Depending upon the packing fraction and degree of orientation of the fibres, the maximum useable depth may be in excess of $10 \mu\text{m}$. In such cases, the confocal technique is preferred over the optical reflection microscopy, because the 'shift of centres' technique will produce more accurate orientation distributions than the moments technique applied to non-elliptical images.

4.2. Matrices

(a) Polyetherethyketone (PEEK) - a common thermoplastic - fluoresces strongly, even without any fibre reinforcements. Epoxy compounds e.g. MY720, MY750, XD927 and LY5210 all fluoresce strongly too. Also, there is evidence to suggest that the fluorescence intensity from these epoxy compounds may be significantly affected by the curing conditions.

(b) Polyester 40-1077 is weakly fluorescing, but reinforcing carbon fibres can still be identified in the matrix and an estimate of maximum useable depth is $\Delta z_m = 5$ to $10 \mu\text{m}$. Another composite, BMI (Bismaleimide) - a one piece thermoset - is weakly fluorescing.

(c) POM, as far as we can tell, does not have a discernible fluorescence signal when no fibre reinforcements, but the 'sizing agents' on the fibres can enable the CLSM technique to be used, as shown in Figure 2.

4.3. Maximum useable depth estimates, Δz_m

The question of the maximum useable depth of a particular matrix/filler combination is more difficult to answer. The usual method adopted to improve the signal/noise ratio is to integrate over a number of frames - hence there is a trade-off between the adequate preprocessing of image fields and the time taken to acquire data. The maximum useable depth depends upon the image processing algorithms employed and more work is needed in this area. Our approach uses a combination of spatial filters and fill routines to obtain fibre image data. The quoted values of Δz_m are conservative estimates for the achievable depth when these standard image processing techniques are employed. An experienced operator, working with an interactive program to locate image centres, could achieve a greater depth. One reason for this is simply that an incomplete 'halo' of fluorescence around a fibre is easy to see by eye, but is difficult to allow for in a 'fully automated' program.

Individual carbon and glass fibres have been followed within a strongly fluorescing matrix to give a $\Delta z_m = 100 \mu\text{m}$. As one might expect, the maximum useable depth is much greater when the matrix is strongly fluorescing than when it is weakly fluorescing. The major problem with carbon fibres in any matrix is the dark 'image trail' produced by the fibre above the optical section which tends to smear out the ideal, elliptical images. The maximum useable depth for carbon reinforcements is really determined by the merging of these 'image trails'.

At this stage, it is clear that, even if the maximum useable depth is between $5 \mu\text{m}$ and $10 \mu\text{m}$, this is enough to remove the ambiguity in colatitude angle, θ even if it cannot improve the accuracy of the determination of (θ, Φ) .

5. FUTURE WORK

We are currently involved in a collaboration with Prof Mattfeldt and colleagues from the University of Ulm to evaluate a new test of 3D isotropy of the fibre orientation distributions, using data from the glass fibres in POM study. Our results are soon to be published[12].

Our immediate aim is to extend the investigation to include ceramic composites and metal matrix composites as well as other polymer matrices. Clearly, there is a need to automate the data collection over a large area (mms x mms) and at different depths. Hence further evaluation of different image processing algorithms and, in particular, the computer control of 'gain' and 'dynamic range' settings on the confocal systems with increasing depth will be necessary for full automation of these 3D orientation distributions.

If the reliable automation of confocal datasets is achieved, this technique would be invaluable for increasing the quality of 3D fibre orientation studies, fibre/fibre interaction work, 'fibre waviness' and even void detection and characterisation.

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